

ENTREPRENEDEU

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

**Quality Assurance Plan
April 2023**

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D1.3 QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN

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Abstract	This document is the main planning document and describes how major aspects of the project are managed, monitored, and controlled. It is intended to provide guidance and direction for specific quality assurance in terms of management, planning, and control activities such as schedule, cost, risk, communication, etc.
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The ENTREPRENEDU Consortium Partners are the following:

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2	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	Fraunhofer	DE
3	EUROPEAN BUSINESS ANGELS NETWORK	EBAN	BE
4	ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS	ATHENA/ CORALLIA	EL
5	KLIYNTEH BULGARIA	CLEANTECH BG	BG
6	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	F6S	IE
7	LUISS LIBERA UNIVERSITÀ INTERNAZIONALE DEGLI STUDI SOCIALI GUIDO CARLI	LUISS	IT
8	PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS	UTH	EL

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The concept of ENTREPRENEDU is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between different regions of the European Union that is causing unbalanced business activities and fewer job opportunities in less developed entrepreneurial ecosystems. In other words, the ENTREPRENEDU project aims to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for European education. To this end, the project seeks to improve the quality and outreach of both innovation and educational ecosystems, implementing a high replicable and scalable Venture Building Program for youth, an educational model for the European entrepreneurial ecosystems developed via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level, supporting concepts and ideas to become concrete solutions, thus enhancing cooperation between businesses and education providers.

The Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) of ENTREPRENEDU describes how the project management team will implement its quality policy. The elaboration of the QAP will allow ENTREPRENEDU partners to define the organisational structure, responsibilities, procedures, processes, and resources needed to implement quality management.

The present QAP is the report that describes the procedures and processes required to ensure that the project will satisfy the needs for which it was undertaken. It includes all the activities of the overall management function that determine the quality policy, objectives, and responsibilities and implements them by means such as quality planning, quality control, quality assurance, and quality improvement, within the quality system.

Research and innovation projects such as ENTREPRENEDU usually generate large sets of activities and involve several parties in their implementation. With this QAP ENTREPRENEDU consortium aims at providing an analysis of the main elements of the quality management policy that will be used in the project and by the partners with regard to the project research development.

Although this report already covers a broad range of aspects related to ENTREPRENEDU quality management, an intermediary internal check will be operated on particular issues foreseeing a final QAP release at the end of the project in M30 (D 1.6). Benefits of creating a QAP include: clearly defining roles, responsibilities, processes and activities; increasing probability that projects will complete on-time, within budget, and with high degree of quality; ensuring understanding of what was agreed upon; helping project teams identify and plan for how project activities will be

managed (budget, quality, schedule, etc.). The intended audience of the ENTREPRENEDU QAP consists of members of the ENTREPRENEDU consortium and the EC Project Adviser.

The first two sections of the QAP offer an introduction and an overview of the procedures and processes set to grant a high level quality assurance. Section 3 introduces quality management while section 4 (project organisation) follows with the project schedule, the description of the project budget, and risk management. The last 4 sections focus on: project communication, project reporting as well as on change management and planning the way forward.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
CA	CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
DoA	DESCRIPTION OF ACTION
Dx.y.	DELIVERABLE Y OF WORK PACKAGE X
EC	EUROPEAN COMMISSION
EU	EUROPEAN UNION
GA	GRANT AGREEMENT
GDPR	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION
G.O.	GENERAL OBJECTIVE
IPR	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS
MIM	MUTUAL INSURANCE MECHANISM
MoU	MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
Mxy	PROJECT MONTH XY
PA	PROJECT ADVISER
PC	PROJECT COORDINATOR
PM	PROJECT MANAGER
QAP	QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN
SMEs	SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES
TC	TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

TRL	TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL
WP	WORK PACKAGE
WPL	WORK PACKAGE LEADER

1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 1.3 details the Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) of the ENTREPRENEDU project. The purpose of this document is to provide a documented plan for the management and control of the organisational, developmental, and supporting processes necessary to the assurance of the quality from the successful implementation of the ENTREPRENEDU project. It outlines the goals and objectives and organisational structure; defines the responsibilities and roles of project participants; identifies the interactions among project partners; and specifies the general procedures and management tools that are implemented to ensure effective quality management and successful project completion. The development of the QAP is an evolving process: the QAP will be updated and revised as needed. Revisions to the QAP will include periodic updates to the plan, especially related to project budget, schedule, and risks. The Project Coordinator will be responsible for the maintenance of and subsequent revisions to the QAP. The project quality management process and procedures included in this QAP are based on the Project Management Body of Knowledge, the PMBOK® Guide, 5th Edition (Rose, 2013), published by the Project Management Institute, and are integrated with practices of modern project management tailored to the needs of the present project. The ENTREPRENEDU project is employing a standard project quality management approach based on documented timelines, regular communications, active follow up, and formal quality control and risk mitigation processes. To support its project quality management approach, the ENTREPRENEDU project uses cloud-shared, revision history-enabled, and always synced folders (provided by Google Drive service) and a set of dedicated conference calls as well as in person meetings. The combination of these solutions provides the team with facilities for sharing and managing of documents, managing work packages and related tasks, tracking progress against task deliverables, scheduling meetings and discussions, and generally ensuring that the distributed project team can pro-actively collaborate to meet project requirements. In order to ensure that regular progress reports are produced on time by deliverable leaders, FEA with the support of F6S created procedures and templates. These procedures have been finalised to assure that actual resource consumption is tracked against plan, that any deviations from the plan are quickly surfaced, and appropriate risk mitigation actions are taken. To facilitate on-going reporting activities and project team work, email lists have been created and conference calling facilities have been established. In addition, a project website has been developed to provide not only internal communications capabilities

for the ENTREPRENEDU team, but to support the team's dissemination and exploitation activities. Finally, formal quality control and risk management processes have been established so that project deliverables meet the operational criteria so that any deviations from plan are properly addressed.

2 OVERVIEW OF ENTREPRENEDU PROJECT

ENTREPRENEDU is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between different regions of the European Union that is causing unbalanced business activities and fewer job opportunities in less developed entrepreneurial ecosystems. ENTREPRENEDU aims to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for European education via a series of three hackathons taking place in Italy, Greece, and Bulgaria during the project development with the objective of selecting at the end of each hackathon the best 4 entrepreneurial ideas that will enter the Business Acceleration programme as proposed by the project partners. Besides these activities, ENTREPRENEDU will create a Venture Building Syllabus that will be tested on 90 students and subsequently fine-tuned for exploitation purposes.

2.1 Project purposes and objectives

The project aims to improve the quality and outreach of both innovation and educational ecosystems, implementing a Venture Building program for youth, thus enhancing cooperation between businesses and education providers.

Therefore, the General Objective (G.O.) of the project ENTREPRENEDU is creating a highly replicable and scalable educational model for both businesses and educational systems via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level, supporting developed concept and ideas (TRL2) to become concrete solutions (TRL5). The program will be validated at the end of the project in 3 different educational entities (2 universities and the "Aspekti" Vocational Training Center of Cleantech Bulgaria). As a consequence, ENTREPRENEDU has the following specific objectives:

- Analysing qualitatively and quantitatively the needs of low and moderate innovative regions in terms of entrepreneurial know-how in education and best case scenarios;
- Assessing and improving, collaboration between developed and less developed innovation ecosystems, quality, capacity, competitiveness, comprehensiveness and outreach of business acceleration services;

- Creating an educational program to strengthen business knowledge and skills, as well as entrepreneurship in less and moderate innovative regions;
- Bringing together regional high-potential start-ups, youth, and business stakeholders to give an impulse to improve the entrepreneurial systems in the regions targeted by the project;
- Evaluating the sustainability of the ENTREPRENEDU methodology and solutions.

ENTREPRENEDU aims at increasing the development of know-how and new entrepreneurs by strengthening the connection between the education system and businesses and including them in collaborative processes, supporting the growth of less developed innovation ecosystems, raising their start-ups and SMEs investors attractiveness and giving them the know – how and knowledge to reach the market:

Figure 1: Graphic representation of the ENTREPRENEDU project

2.2 Project milestones

For a correct tracking of progress, the ENTREPRENEDU project adopts a work plan with seven Milestones as reported in the table below:

Table 1: ENTREPRENEDU milestones table

Milestones					
<i>Grant Preparation (Milestones screen)</i>					
Milestone No	Milestone Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
1	ENTREPRENEDU kick-off	WP1	1-FEA	Minutes of Meeting of the kick-off.	1
2	Context analysis	WP2	7-LUISS	Public guideline related to needs analysis.	6
3	Cross-fertilisation analysis	WP3	4-ATHENA/CORALLIA	Hackathons implementation report.	22
4	Business Acceleration	WP4	2-Fraunhofer	Mentoring modules implemented	23
5	Venture Building programme	WP5	3-EBAN	Educational model implemented and validated.	30
6	Exploitation strategy	WP6	5-CLEANTECH BG	Business plan on the ENTREPRENEDU model.	30
7	Dissemination and communication strategy	WP7	6-F6S	Dissemination and communication plan.	30

2.3 Project deliverables

A set of deliverables in chronological order of delivery is identified in the table below as a concrete output of the project's activities implementation:

Cod.	Deliverable	Date	Month	WP	Partner
D1.1	Kick-off Minutes	14-02-2023	1	WP1	1 - FEA
D7.1	Dissemination and communication plan	14-03-2023	2	WP7	6 - F6S
D1.2	Data Management Plan	14-04-2023	3	WP1	1 - FEA
D1.3	Quality Assurance Plan	14-04-2023	3	WP1	1 - FEA
D2.1	Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario	14-05-2023	4	WP2	7 - LUISS
D3.1	Hackathon Handbook Template	14-06-2023	5	WP3	4 - ATHENA/CORALLIA
D2.2	Public guideline on specific needs for low moderate innovation regions	14-07-2023	6	WP2	7 - LUISS
D4.1	Mentoring modules	14-08-2023	7	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D4.3	Feedback collection	14-08-2023	7	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D1.4	Internal progress report	14-01-2024	12	WP1	1 - FEA
D4.2	Report on mentoring activities	14-03-2024	14	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D4.4	Mentoring modules - final release	14-08-2024	19	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D4.5	Report on mentoring activities - final release	14-08-2024	19	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D5.1	Call for students	14-08-2024	19	WP5	3 - EBAN
D4.6	Feedback collection - final release	14-09-2024	20	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer

D5.2	Syllabus of the Venture Building course	14-09-2024	20	WP5	3 - EBAN
D5.3	Venture Building course Teaching Material	14-09-2024	20	WP5	3 - EBAN
D3.2	Hackathons implementation report	14-11-2024	22	WP3	4 - ATHENA/CORALLIA
D5.4	Fine-tuning survey on the venture building program and related Fellowship	14-02-2025	25	WP5	3 - EBAN
D7.2	Dissemination and communication plan - final release	14-02-2025	25	WP7	6 - F6S
D6.1	Business plan on ENTREPRENEDU model	14-05-2025	28	WP6	5 - CLEANTECH BG
D6.2	Publication of 3 guidelines on the ENTREPRENEDU standard operating procedures	14-05-2025	28	WP6	5 - CLEANTECH BG
D1.5	Data Management Plan - final release	14-07-2025	30	WP1	1 - FEA
D1.6	Quality Assurance Plan - final release	14-07-2025	30	WP1	1 - FEA
D6.3	3 MoUs signed with other EU initiatives and/or educational entities	14-07-2025	30	WP6	5 - CLEANTECH BG

3 QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Quality management is the process of defining the strategy and methods the project will deploy to ensure the project's deliverables are of acceptable quality before they are delivered. Quality management addresses all the issues related to quality assurance, self-assessment and any ethical issues. All ethical issues are specifically addressed in deliverable D1.2 (Data Management Plan).

Project Quality management is fundamental to the success of the project, and the project adopts a methodology with three separated processes:

- *Quality Planning* which identifies the quality standards relevant to the project and determines how to satisfy them;
- *Quality assurance* which is the execution of processes and procedures to ensure the achievement of quality, to assure that the project satisfies the needs for which it was undertaken;
- *Quality control* which verifies and assesses the achievement/product; it is concerned with the operational activities and techniques that are used to fulfil the requirements of quality.

Quality management is the responsibility of the Project Coordinator (PC) which ensures quality of the project management and, consequently, of all deliverables, and provides measurement criteria to verify the success of the project.

The Work Plan of the ENTREPRENEDU project describes milestones and the acceptance criteria for each phase of the project. Assessing adherence to these baseline conditions provides the method for evaluating both the project and its services.

Quality organisation is under the responsibility of the PC. The PC is supported by the Project Manager (PM) in the definition and in the execution of the control activities planned or considered useful during the ENTREPRENEDU project. The PC receives also support, advice, and help at several levels:

- from Work Package leaders in several quality functions related to the delivery process. Activities leaders are fully responsible for scientific and technical quality check of all deliverables.
- from the European Commission. The European Commission, through the Project Adviser, may provide advice on any quality issue related to the project. The Work Package Leaders may also request advice from the Project Officer on quality issues whenever necessary, usually communicating through the PC.

The PC is in charge of ensuring that deliverables to be submitted are structured, harmonised, and organised to ensure that they are timely, exhaustive, clear, and effective.

3.1 Document production process

During the project, many kinds of documents will be produced. It is crucial to define common formats of documents, and uniform rules of their description, responsibilities, revision plans, and revision procedures.

When producing any document to be distributed to at least one other partner of the project, each contributor shall apply the rules below, in particular:

- Produce the document in an electronic file with the same name as the File Name;
- Use the English language;

- Use the appropriate template;

Deliverables structure:

- A front page with general data about the document and the ENTREPRENEDU logo
- Version history
- A table of contents
- An Executive summary
- An introduction including the scope of the document
- Sections constituting the body of the document
- Possible Annexes
- Page numbering

The different actors involved in the production of documents are:

- Document leader: is the deliverable responsible as indicated in the deliverable list
- Other contributors: are the partners/beneficiaries involved in the activities related to the Deliverable
- WP/Task leader
- Project Coordinator (PC)

The document leader is the person in charge of the production of a document. The production rules and guidelines and the document rules have to be applied under their responsibility.

3.2 Deliverables monitoring and control

The monitoring process should envisage in advance possible problems connected to the development of tasks and the production of deliverables. To facilitate communicating progress on each deliverable, each WP Leader (WPL) reports progress and issues on deliverable production and on the work package implementation during monthly meetings' calls.

Deliverables are generated under the responsibility of the WPL, who will be charged with ensuring that all deliverables are prepared correctly and in time.

Each project deliverable will be the target of a peer review by two reviewers before being submitted to the Commission, to guarantee that it meets the objectives of the project as a whole. The limit date for reception of comments is 5 working days.

During the review the PC checks if the deliverable meets the formal requirements regarding the file format, and naming and versioning schemes. Furthermore, they monitor and maintain the review process itself.

The document leader is in charge of the update of a document after internal review. They receive the comments from the reviewers, address all comments, and take into account the accepted ones.

The quality control process for deliverables requires that the deliverable owners and reviewers ensure that the deliverables adhere to the following quality aspects:

1. the contribution of the deliverable to the WP and the overall goals of ENTREPRENEDU project should be clearly stated;
2. the objectives of the deliverable should be clearly expressed. Specifically, the deliverable should feature a short 1-2 paragraphs introduction that clearly states the role and duty of said document, in the scope of ENTREPRENEDU;
3. the deliverable should be clearly related to previous and future deliverables in the WP and – if applicable – to deliverables from other WPs;
4. the relation / additions / differences to previous deliverables in the same work package (i.e., in the case the deliverable is an improved version of a previous one) should be clearly stated;
5. the deliverable should be a self-contained document, which can be understood without knowledge of the DoA (or previous deliverables);
6. the deliverable contents should be consistent with its description in the DoA; if not, the deviation should be explained;
7. the deliverable should be cohesive and concise (typically not more than 50-60 pages);
8. the deliverable should not contain any claims that are not proven or supported by references.

The final version of the deliverables must be submitted to the Project Coordinator in Word and pdf formats. The pdf is the electronic format requested by the EC for the

submission of all the deliverables/documents elaborated during the project. If finally approved, public deliverables will be published via the project web site.

In order to grant a high-quality Quality Assurance and Management Plan, the following sections provide detailed guidance on all the required activities for proper project coordination, implementation, and development.

4 PROJECT ORGANISATION

4.1 Management structure

The coordination of the ENTREPRENEDU project requires special attention to the quality management of multidisciplinary activities in order to define an organisation that meets the overall ENTREPRENEDU project objectives, with the right balance between rigour and flexibility and giving room to innovation and creativity. Special attention must also be paid to the content of each WP in order to ensure the maximum consistency and solidity in the project.

The main objective of the quality management is to ensure that all project-related tasks are performed successfully and comply with contractual requirements. The key features for successful project quality management are:

- a management organisation that is matched with the project complexity;
- efficient communications within the organisation;
- clear definition of contractual requirements and relationships;
- adequate planning and control procedures;
- comprehensive quality and risk management frameworks.

In order to achieve efficient project implementation, the structures of the Work Packages and their related tasks have been defined with the aim of minimising overlap between different activities. The efficient relation among tasks and WPs in the ENTREPRENEDU work-plan allows a clear definition of responsibilities, roles and objectives for all project resources. Within the project, each partner has a clear responsibility and lines of reporting: each task activity in a WP is led by a partner, with the task leader reporting to the work package leader, coordinating the technical work for their activity according to the project and WP objectives.

The management structure is based on the extensive experience of the partners in European funded projects and has been adapted in order to meet the requirements

of a project that is characterised by an ambitious activity plan and a heterogeneous consortium. The ENTREPRENEDU main elements of the project organisations are:

- A. the Project Coordinator, acting as the general manager and overseeing the technical progress of ENTREPRENEDU;
- B. the Project Manager, supporting the Project Coordinator in administrative, financial and management issues;
- C. the Work Package Leaders, responsible for successful execution of the work packages;
- D. the Steering Committee, chaired by the Coordinator and one senior representative of each partner, is the decision-making body of the consortium;
- E. the Technical Committee, responsible for the day-by-day technical project management activities, is constituted by the Project Coordinator and the WP leaders.

4.2 Roles and responsibilities

The ENTREPRENEDU project is being implemented through the concerted efforts of various organisations and responsible parties, who work together as an integrated team providing multiple levels of oversight to ensure a successful outcome for the project. This subsection describes the responsibilities for the main roles and presents the persons already appointed to cover the specific roles.

- Role: Project Coordinator (PC)

Appointed Person: Eleonora Lombardi (FEA)

Main Responsibilities: The PC is the primary responsible for the ENTREPRENEDU project and acts as the intermediary between the Consortium and the European Commission. They are also responsible for the overall coordination of the project execution, and work on the day-to-day management of the project in collaboration with the Project Manager. In particular, the Project Coordinator is responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations;
- collecting, reviewing, and submitting information on the progress of the project, reports, and other deliverables to the EC;
- preparing the meetings, proposing decisions, and preparing the agenda of Project Management Board meetings, chairing the meetings, and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings;
- transmitting promptly documents and information connected with the Project;

- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents which are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.

The Project Coordinator is assisted in their role and responsibilities by the Project Manager.

- Role: Project Manager (PM)

Appointed Person: Valerio Roscani (FEA)

Main Responsibilities: The PM is responsible for overseeing the Administrative and Financial Management of the project, managing advance payments, transferring the sums allocated among the contractors as per budget, and record-keeping of EC payments allocated/paid to the contractors. The PM also supports the PC in making sure that the project is managed using the highest standards and procedures in compliance with the recognised international standards for project management set by the Project Management Institute (PMI). They are responsible for ensuring that all key deliverables are met within time, cost, and performance constraints, and that they adhere to proper quality control mechanisms and standards. The PM must ensure that all assigned resources are effectively and efficiently utilised and that the project is properly resourced with both internal and external resources. They are in charge of: regular status reports and updates to executives; ensuring that all partners are kept informed and up-to-date as to what their responsibilities are in relation to the project; budget tracking actual against estimated; assistance to the Project Coordinator in the day-to-day management of the Project.

- Role: Work Package Leader (WPL)

Appointed Persons: Valerio Roscani (FEA), Henry Nicolai (Fraunhofer IPK), Natalia Costanzo (EBAN), Ina Todorova (Cleantech Bulgaria), Daniel Silva (F6S), Christian Lechner (LUISS), Nektaria Berikou (Corallia).

Main Responsibilities: Each WPL is responsible for the planning, progress control, quality management, and the successful completion of their WP and of the interactions with the other WPs according to the work plan. Their activities include:

- keeping work package on track and report WP status to the PC;
- Planning and distributing among WP partners actions transmitted by the PC and monitoring their execution;

- supervising the work of the WP team, identifying problems and risks, and, when necessary, proposing revisions of the WP plan.
- Role: Steering Committee (SC)

Appointed Persons: Eleonora Lombardi (FEA), Henry Nicolai (Fraunhofer IPK), Natalia Costanzo (EBAN), Ina Todorova (Cleantech Bulgaria), Daniel Silva (F6S), Christian Lechner (LUISS), Nektaria Berikou (Corallia), Achilleas Barlas (University of Thessaly).

Main Responsibilities: Each member has a vote and decisions are made by majority. It is the consortium's decision-making and arbitration board of the project. The SC supervises the development of planned activities and defines the overall project strategy, considering long-term interests of the project and fulfilment of the Grant Agreement (GA) commitments. It is responsible for: consortium's budget and financial allocation of EC's contribution among various activities, annual validation of realised expenditures according to the budget, monitoring of external risks which may impair progress towards objectives, proposing strategies and contingency plans to address those risks, any issue related to modifications and amendments of the GA and the CA (e.g., project duration extension and budget reallocation), withdrawal, inclusion or exclusion of a consortium member, conflicts within partners of the consortium for any issue contemplated in the CA.

- Role: Technical Committee (TC)

Appointed Persons: Eleonora Lombardi (FEA), Henry Nicolai (Fraunhofer IPK), Natalia Costanzo (EBAN), Ina Todorova (Cleantech Bulgaria), Daniel Silva (F6S), Christian Lechner (LUISS), Nektaria Berikou (Corallia), Achilleas Barlas (University of Thessaly).

Main Responsibilities: The TC is responsible for the day-by-day technical project management activities. They: report on progresses towards project's objectives, monitor technical progresses and achievements, take corrective measures/contingency plans, review internal work plans (especially for activities across WPs), ensure deliverables/reports are of good technical quality/timely issued, discuss about common exploitation/dissemination actions and other innovation-related activities. TC meets via video/teleconference once a month, with face-to-face meetings every 6 months or more frequently if needed. In all cases, decision-making powers, voting rights of its members, majority requirements as well as convocation conditions, notices, chairmanship and other aspects are regulated in the CA to ensure the maximum efficiency and the control on project direction.

An organisation based on these roles provides a good balance between striving for a light organisational load and detailing a structure that fits with the complex of a project like ENTREPRENEDU. The table below shows the management figures and responsibilities:

Table 2: Table of management figures and their responsibilities

Management category	Responsibility	Appointed body
General Management	Overall direction and major decisions of the project; communication, control and corrective measures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Coordinator (PC) - Work Package Leaders
Financial and day-to-day management	Supervision of deliverables preparation and submission, organisation of project meetings and reviews, control overall project expenditure, cost report collection, check and payment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Manager (PM)
Scientific and technical management	Coordination of operative efforts on a scientific, technical, services and business related basis, responsible for scientific, technical and business decisions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Coordinator (PC) - WP Leaders (WPL) - Technical Committee - Steering Committee
Consultancy, Exploitation, Dissemination	Monitoring, consultancy feed-back, exploitation and dissemination of the results of the project in order to provide fundamental impact and boost the adoption of project results outside the Consortium.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Coordinator (PC) - WP Leaders (WPL) - Technical Committee - Steering Committee

4.3 Consortium procedures

Day-to-day scientific and management decisions are taken by the PC. Strategic decisions and major technical and operational decisions (like any reschedule of deliverables, milestones, tasks, effort) are taken by the Steering Committee, which has the highest decision-making responsibility and policy-setting power.

The Steering Committee shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (quorum). Each member shall have

one vote. Defaulting Parties may not vote. In case of conflict resolution voting, a majority of 80% is required. The PC mediates and participates in all important decisions.

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if the PC circulates to all members a written document which is then signed by the defined majority of members. Such a document shall include the deadline for responses. Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the minutes has been accepted.

A member who can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of the Steering Committee may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision. When the decision is foreseen on the original agenda, a member may veto such a decision during the meeting only. When a decision has been made on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a member may veto such a decision during the meeting and within 15 days after the draft minutes of the meeting are sent. In case of exercise of veto, the members shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all members. A Party may not veto decisions relating to its identification as a Defaulting Party. The Defaulting Party may not veto decisions relating to its participation and termination in the consortium or the consequences of them. A Party requesting to leave the consortium may not veto decisions relating thereto.

The PC produces written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. They send draft minutes to all members within 10 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes are considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no member has sent an objection in writing to the PC with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes. The PC sends the accepted minutes to all the members of the Steering Committee.

The Steering Committee is free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out.

4.4 Issue management

Conflict is not expected to be a significant factor since the roles of each partner have been well defined, so as to avoid any misunderstandings that might occur later in the project. The resolution of problems and conflicts is handled systematically. Establishing a good working relationship among the project team members is a

prerequisite for the quick resolution of problems and issues. Conflicts' resolution is based on the principle that any dispute should be resolved by consent and as near the source as possible, thus, conflicts on a local sphere are managed by the people involved (e.g., a dispute between the partners engaged in a WP should be addressed by that WP team). Conflicts which cannot be solved internally are taken through a "principled negotiation" process that is focused on optimising outcomes and maximising the benefits of all parties involved.

In case of conflicts arising within the consortium regarding the carrying out of the project or other matters related to the project itself, the following steps are taken:

1. The parties try to resolve the conflict issue amicably between them.
2. If a conflict cannot be resolved within the local sphere, it is raised to the PC; for conflict resolution in a technical aspect, the PC is in charge of proposing an alternative. If this is agreed, the issue is solved.
3. If this attempt fails, the question is brought to the first scheduled meeting of the SC, or in case of urgency, an ad hoc meeting of the SC is called for by the Project Coordinator, upon request of a SC member;
4. The question is discussed within the SC, and the Project Coordinator tries to solve it by consensus; the SC decides which procedure will be followed, and the corresponding correction measures that should be taken. The participant that provokes the conflict declares acceptance of the procedure and the corrective measures.
5. If the conflict cannot be resolved, the PC declares the participant "not in line" with the project execution and the Consortium asks for a contract termination for the participant concerned, with the contractually stated consequences. The EC Project Adviser is immediately notified of the situation and of the measures to be taken in order to solve it. An appropriate revision of the work plan is suggested by the PC, approved by the SC, and sent to the commission for acceptance.
6. In case it is decided (by the PC or SC) that a conflict resolution involves a voting procedure among partners, a majority of the 75% is required for the decision to go ahead (6 out of 8 partners).

4.5 Stakeholders (Internal and external)

Management of stakeholders' engagement is carried out within WP2, although strong links have been activated with WP6 and WP7 activities both in dissemination and

communication as well as in exploitation. Stakeholders are considered key drivers to project exploitation so their selection is going to be done among target audience categories with priorities given to decision makers and opinion leaders. It is mandatory to include in stakeholders going to be engaged representatives of institutions, social communities, business actors and research excellences. A first exercise to identify all key stakeholder categories is summarised in the table below:

Table 3: Table representing the stakeholder categories identified for ENTREPRENEDU

ID	Description	Interest(s)	Observations
STK #1	Project partners	Active participants in the project development	Already engaged
STK #2	End users	Startups and SMEs in the scaleup phase applying for ENTREPRENEDU services	D&C activities to attract and interest them
STK #3	European Commission	Project enabler, Research outcomes and their evaluation	Already engaged
STK #4	Business entities	Business exploitation around ENTREPRENEDU outcomes should be designed around their needs	D&C plan designed to engage them
STK #5	Scientific community	Scientific exploitation of achieved results	Scientific dissemination designed to support their engagement.

For each identified stakeholder category an analysis of their interests and whether those interests are in favour or against the goals of the project is conducted by the task leader and the support of the whole consortium. For those stakeholders that it is considered appropriate, pro-active engagement plans are defined and conducted. On a regular basis, a review of the stakeholder list is done to identify new (if any) stakeholders and to assess the engagement and attitude of each stakeholder. When needed, new engagement plans will be defined and launched and already existing engagement plans will be modified.

5 PROJECT SCHEDULE

An overall ENTREPRENEDU high-level schedule has been prepared by the PM including the different phases, duration and delivery time:

Table 4: Table representing the GANTT of ENTREPRENEDU

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	
Hackathons										H2	H3																				
Mentoring					H1						M																				
Venture Building Programme Validation																															
Milestones	M					M																	M	M						M	
WP1 Project Management and Coordination																															
T1.1 General Assembly meetings	GA					GA						GA										GA								GA	
T1.2 Reporting and internal communication	D1.1											D1.4																			
T1.3 Data Management				D1.2																											D1.5
T1.4 Quality Assurance				D1.3																											D1.6
WP2 Context analysis and stakeholders setting																															
T2.1 Success cases and go-to-business scenario					D2.1																										
T2.2 Needs identification for low and moderate innovative regions						D2.2																									
WP3 Hackathons, trainings and awareness raising initiatives																															
T3.1 Hackathons' design and implementation plan					D3.1																										
T3.2 Pre-hackathon campaign -Information sessions																															
T3.3 Launch of the Call for the Hackathons (registration, selection)																															
T3.4 Hackathons' implementation																														D3.2	
WP4 Supporting Business Acceleration																															
T4.1 Coordination and definition of mentoring activities													D4.2																		
T4.2 Elaboration and delivery of mentoring modules							D4.1																								
T4.3 Post Hackathons interview from participants and stakeholders							D4.3																								
WP5 Venture Building Program and validation																															
T5.1 Venture Building Syllabus																															
T5.2 Selection of students for the validation phase																															
T5.3 Venture Building Program course and mentoring																															
T5.4 Venture Fellowship program																															
WP6 Venture Building Program refinement and mutual learning																															
T6.1 Establish guidelines and standard operating procedures in line with those adopted in the considered ENTREPRENEDU countries																														D6.2	
T6.2 Synergies of the project with other existing programs and initiatives																															
T6.3 Business plan and related ENTREPRENEDU model exploitation																														D6.3	
WP7 Communication and dissemination																															
T7.1 Dissemination and communication strategy					D7.1																									D7.2	
T7.2 Networking and dissemination activities																															

5.1 Schedule management

Schedule management is the process of ensuring that the quality of the project schedule is baselined, maintained, and managed. It is a dynamic process that occurs throughout the project lifecycle: under the rolling wave approach, as more information becomes available, the schedule can be refined to reflect the updated information. Schedule management is accomplished through a stringent change control process, and a comprehensive monitoring and reporting system. Project status is monitored against the baseline on a monthly basis and the Work-Plan is

updated as needed. The PM has primary responsibility for coordinating the gathering of schedule status information from all partners.

The project overall schedule management is the responsibility of the Project Coordinator; the schedule management within each WP is managed by the WPL; the detailed action plan for each task is managed by the leader of that task; thus, the different schedule management processes are therefore managed by different people depending on the level.

As the monthly monitoring is performed, the PM may identify schedule slippage on critical paths tasks: the PM and the PC will work together to identify ways to get the project back on schedule.

For variances greater than 1 month, the PM may choose to ask guidance of the SC. Variances greater than 3 months are considered unacceptable. The PM and PC will immediately inform the SC if they determine that any milestones are at risk of being missed.

If a change occurs, the PM shall incorporate proposed change(s) into an updated work-plan. This document contains a revision history log where the following information should be recorded:

- the increment version number;
- the date;
- the name of the person authorising the change;
- the description of the change;
- the effects of the change on the progress of the work.

Revisions to schedule baselines (only in cases in which a milestone is missed) are managed and controlled by the change management plan.

The approved schedule Plan is stored in the ENTREPRENEDU Google Drive repository, maintained by the PM and available to all project teams.

5.2 Action item management

Actionable activities are traced by the relevant minutes of meetings and teleconferences. Each action includes the following information:

- action identifier;
- action responsible;

- action deadline.

Actions can have three different states which depend on the current level of accomplishment:

- an action is IN PROGRESS if it has been initiated but is not yet managed;
- an action is DONE if there is evidence that somebody accomplished the action;
- an action is DELAYED if it is postponed with respect to the fixed date.

The PM is in charge of managing the project action items list which is stored in the ENTREPRENEDU repository. The action item list is checked and discussed during plenary and technical teleconferences.

6 PROJECT BUDGET

To finance the project and ensure a high quality of performance and that all partners have access to a sufficient level of resources, the total budget of ENTREPRENEDU accounts for EUR 1,048,950.03, 100% EU granted over 30 months.

As specified in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, the financial contribution of the Funding Authority to the ENTREPRENEDU project is distributed by the Project Coordinator.

The coordinator must distribute the payments between the beneficiaries without unjustified delay.

The following payments will be made to the Coordinator:

- one pre-financing payment;
- one or more interim payments, on the basis of the request(s) for interim payment;
- one payment of the balance, on the basis of the request for payment of the balance.

The aim of the pre-financing is to provide the beneficiaries with a float. It remains the property of the EU until the payment of the balance. The Agency will make the pre-financing payment to the coordinator 30 days from entry into force/10 days before starting date – whichever is the latest. An amount of EUR 52,447.50, corresponding to 5% of the maximum grant amount, is retained by the Agency from

the initial pre-financing payment and transferred into the Mutual Insurance Mechanism (MIM). Interim and final payments are made subject to project deliverables. The consortium will duly report on the progress of ENTREPRENEDU project in accordance with the reporting calendar set out in the Grant Agreement.

The Agency will pay to the coordinator the amount due as final payment within 90 days from receiving the periodic report. The payment of the balance closes the financial aspects of the grant (partial payment for partially completed WPs possible) and releases the amount retained for the Mutual Insurance Mechanism.

ENTREPRENEDU foresees the following periodic reporting and payments:

Figure 2: Figure representing ENTREPRENEDU's reporting and payment schedule

Reporting					Payments	
Reporting periods			Type	Deadline	Type	Deadline (time to pay)
RP No	Month from	Month to				
					Initial prefinancing	30 days from entry into force/10 days before starting date – whichever is the latest
1	1	18	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
2	19	30	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Final payment	90 days from receiving periodic report

- Initial pre-financing: the aim of the pre-financing is to provide the beneficiaries with a float. It remains the property of the EU until the final payment. For initial prefinancings, the amount due, schedule and modalities are set out in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement.
- Interim payment: Interim payments reimburse the eligible lump sum contributions claimed for work packages implemented during the reporting periods. Interim payments will be made in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet (see Point 4.2). Payment is subject to the

approval of the periodic report and the work packages declared. The interim payment will be calculated by the granting authority in the following steps: Step 1 – Calculation of the total accepted EU contribution; Step 2 – Limit to the interim payment ceiling.

- Final payment: The final payment (payment of the balance) reimburses the remaining eligible lump sum contributions claimed for the implemented work packages. Final payments can also pay partially completed work packages. The final payment will be made in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement. Payment is subject to the approval of the final periodic report and the work packages declared. Their approval does not imply recognition of compliance, authenticity, completeness or correctness of their content. Work packages (or parts of them) that have not been delivered or cannot be approved will be rejected (see Article 27 of the Grant Agreement). The final grant amount for the action will be calculated in the following steps: Step 1 – Calculation of the total accepted EU contribution.

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement.

6.1 Budget/Cost management

ENTREPRENEDU is a lump-sum grant and, as such, the overall lump sum is fixed in the grant agreement. The breakdown of lump sum shares per beneficiary and per work package is included in the grant agreement (Annex 2). The detailed cost estimates from ENTREPRENEDU proposal is not part of the grant agreement. Once the lump sum is fixed in the grant agreement, the costs actually incurred are not relevant.

This calls for budget flexibility as follows: ENTREPRENEDU consortium members can use the budget as they see fit as long as the project is implemented as agreed. The actual distribution of the lump sum is invisible to the EC. However, budget transfers require an amendment if the consortium wants to reflect them in the grant agreement.

Transfers between Work Packages are possible if:

- Work Packages concerned are not already completed (and declared in a financial statement).
- Justified by the technical and scientific implementation of the action.

The reporting is done by using a standard reporting template. The coordinator declares work packages as “Completed” or “Not Completed”. This should be justified

by the technical periodic report. An incomplete work package can be completed and be paid in a subsequent reporting period. At the final reporting period, it is possible to declare “Partially Completed” work packages, and to enter the percentage of completion. The completion of work packages is not based on a successful outcome, but on the completion of activities as described in the description of action.

The financial report is much simplified and, to a large extent, automated. The financial statement for all beneficiaries is automatically generated (based on the accepted work packages and the corresponding lump sum shares). The ‘use of resources’ report (certificates on financial statements) is not required for lump sum grants.

Work packages are accepted if the activities have been carried out. EC can also accept them when all essential tasks have been completed, when equivalent tasks have been carried out, or when deviations have been justified. Lump sum projects can be amended according to scientific-technical needs (or deviations can be justified in the reports). These mechanisms are used to make completion of work packages feasible. Before a lump sum work package (that is declared completed by the project consortium) is rejected as incomplete, the consortium is invited to respond to the observations of the project officer. If the rejection is upheld the lump sum share concerned is not paid at that point in time. The consortium should complete the work package later and declare it at the end of any subsequent reporting period. If it is not possible to complete a work package by the end of the project (e.g., for technical reasons or due to force majeure), the lump sum is paid partially in line with the degree of completion. The decision on the partial amount is taken on a case-by-case basis. The consortium members will be able to provide observations.

Below the summary of the dos and don'ts for financial reporting:

Figure 3: Figure representing dos and don'ts of financial reporting

Keeping records

You need (e.g.)

- Technical documents
- Publications, prototypes, deliverables
- Documentation required by good research practices such as lab books
- ...any document proving that the work was done as detailed in Annex 1

Same as for all Horizon Europe grants

You don't need

- Time-sheets
- Pay-slips or contracts
- Depreciation policy
- Invoices
- ...actual costs

7 RISK MANAGEMENT

In order to grant the quality of the project, ENTREPRENEDU recognises the importance of maximising the results of positive events and minimising the consequences of adverse events. For this purpose, risk management is key for a proper project quality management. According to the PMBOK® Guide, a risk is “an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, has a positive or negative effect on one or more project objectives such as scope, schedule, cost, or quality”. For the purpose of this document, only uncertain events with a potential negative impact are considered. If the foreseen event or condition takes place, it becomes an actual issue to be dealt with by the project’s Consortium. From this perspective, Risk Management is the identification, assessment, and prioritisation of risks to minimise, monitor, and control the probability and/or impact of unfortunate events also known as threats. Since not all risks can be eliminated, mitigation strategies and contingency plans can be developed to lessen their impact if they occur. Essentially, effective risk management requires an informed understanding of relevant risks, an assessment of their relative priority and a rigorous approach to monitoring and controlling them. The responsibility of managing project risks relies upon the Coordinator: identified risks are tackled and alerts are raised in case any of the identified risks increases its priority. All activities related with the risk management are monitored by the PM with collaboration of each WP leader for specific issues relevant within every specific WP.

7.1 Risk management strategy

The Risk Management activities are applied to the ENTREPRENEDU project to attempt to decrease the probability and impact of negative events by identifying and planning for risks before significant negative consequences occur. This section describes the process used to identify, classify, document, and track risks during the project. The risk management lifecycle consists of the following steps, as shown below:

Figure 4: Figure representing the risk management lifecycle

These steps are executed in sequence for each project risk introduced in the risk management process. Each WPL develops a specific risk management plan for the WPs they are managing. These WP-specific risk management plans are rolled-up into a single risk management plan for the whole project. The most commonly used tool to record information about risks is the Risk Register, which acts as a central repository for all identified potential threats of the project. Prepared by the PM (with inputs from all members), the Risk Register is used to identify, classify, organise, evaluate, and track all levels of risks that may affect the project. Mitigation strategies are then identified and tracked for implementation at appropriate times during the timeline of the project. The Risk Register is maintained by the Project Manager and is constantly updated as the project evolves. The most critical risks in the risk register are reviewed as a standing agenda item of the project’s monthly plenary meetings. During these reviews, each risk is considered to see how it has changed since the last meeting, to monitor the status of risk mitigation measures, and to determine if any actions need to be taken to further reduce the risk. Finally, new risks will be identified, assessed and strategies for mitigating them will be developed.

7.2 Risk identification

Risk Identification is the proactive process of uncovering risks which might affect the project before they turn into problems. Risk identification is an iterative process. The first phase of risk identification occurred during the proposal phase of the project; the risks identified during the proposal phase have been re-examined and updated

based on the current state of the project. This process of ongoing updating will continue throughout the lifecycle of the project. Participants in risk identification include subject-matter experts, WPLs, and project management and team members. Identified risks are documented in the risk register and discussed/reviewed during the monthly project meetings. Risks may span through various aspects including those that are political, design-related, procurement-related, environmental, technical, organisational, external, and/or economical. For ENTREPRENEDU, two main categories have been initially used, i.e. project-level risks and WP-level risks. Each time a new risk is detected it shall be managed. Nevertheless, the biggest effort has to be put at the beginning in order to anticipate, as far as possible, the monitoring of possible risks, and plan, if the case, mitigation actions.

7.3 Risk analysis, qualification, and prioritisation

Risk Analysis is the most detailed phase of the entire risk management process. It involves evaluating and prioritising the risks. Evaluating a risk involves establishing values for its potential effect on scope, cost and/or schedule of the project. A determination is made as to the:

- probability (likelihood) of the risk occurring;
- ability to mitigate the risk;
- potential effect of the risk.

There are two primary methods for conducting risk analysis:

- qualitative: assessing the probability and impact of risks;
- quantitative: using mathematical methods to objectively assess the probability and impact of risks.

The determination of risk probability (likelihood of occurrence) and impact (degree of its effect) is a subjective process which considers the criticality of internal and external project factors within the specific context of the ENTREPRENEDU project. The probability and the impact for each identified risk are assessed using the following approach:

Probability

- Very Low – (<10%)
- Low – (10-29%)
- Medium – (30-50%)
- High – (51-70%)

- Very High – (>70%)

Impact

- Very High (Catastrophic) – Risk that has a catastrophic impact on project cost, schedule or performance.
- High (Major) – Risk that has a major impact on project cost, schedule or performance.
- Medium (Significant) – Risk that has the potential to significantly impact project cost, schedule or performance.
- Low (Minimal) – Risk that has relatively minimal impact on cost, schedule or performance.
- Very Low (Trivial) – Risk that has only a trivial impact on cost, schedule or performance.

The combination of probability and impact is used to evaluate the risk level (Low, Medium or High) and to get a list of the prioritised risks. The Impact and Probability matrix is then elaborated by assigning different colours to each risk:

1. **green** shows a low risk level;
2. **yellow** shows a medium risk level;
3. **red** shows a high risk level, which requires constant monitoring.

7.4 Risk response planning

Risk response is the process of deciding what should be done with a risk, if anything at all. Risk response answers two key questions:

- (1) who owns the risk (responsibility)
- (2) what can / should be done (scope and actions).

Strategies and plans are developed to minimise the effects of a risk to a point where the risk can be controlled and managed. For each major risk, a risk response plan is developed. The range of response actions for the project is as follows:

1. **Transfer:** risk is external to the project. Resources and knowledge outside of the project are better able to manage the risk. Transfer implies the ultimate accountability, responsibility, and authority to expend resources, it requires acceptance of the risk by the receiving party. Transferring liability for risk is most effective in dealing with financial risk exposure.

2. **Accept:** do nothing, but handle the risk as an issue if it occurs. However, no further resources are expended in managing the risk. These are usually risks of lower significance.
3. **Avoid:** determine actions that, if executed enough in advance, will prevent the risk from occurring
4. **Mitigate:** eliminate or reduce the risk by reducing the impact, reducing the probability, or shifting the timeframe when action must be taken.
5. **Watch:** monitor the risks for early warning of critical changes in impact, probability, timeframe or other aspects.
6. **Contingency:** determine actions that are executed once the risk has occurred to address the situation (actions taken especially to minimise adverse consequences).

For all identified risks, the various handling techniques should be evaluated in terms of feasibility, expected effectiveness, cost, and schedule implications, and the effect on the system's technical quality and performance. The Project Manager, together with the concerned WP and Task Leaders, is responsible for developing and evaluating different risk handling strategies that are best fitted to the project's circumstances. The Project Manager is also responsible for monitoring and controlling the performance of risk handling actions.

7.5 Risk monitoring and control

Risk Monitoring is the process of keeping track of the risks and evaluating the effectiveness of the response actions. Monitoring may also provide a basis for developing additional response actions and identifying new risks and is done in a continuous manner. The level of critical risks on the ENTREPRENEDU project is tracked, monitored, and reported regularly, with specific discussions during the monthly meetings' calls. As more risks are identified, they are qualified and added to the risk management strategy to ensure they are monitored at the appropriate times and adequate response strategies are developed. During risk monitoring and control the following tasks are performed:

1. identifying, analysing, and planning for new risks;
2. reviewing project performance information (such as progress/status reports, issues, and corrective actions);
3. re-analysing existing risks to see if the probability, impact, or proper response plan has changed;
4. reviewing the execution of risk responses and analysing their effectiveness;

5. reviewing the effectiveness of the risk process to determine whether changes to the approach, tools or techniques are required.

7.6 ENTREPRENEDU Critical risks identification and risk management strategy

The ENTREPRENEDU Critical risks identification and risk management strategy has already been implemented by and it is reported here:

Table 5: Table representing ENTREPRENEDU's critical risk identification and risk management strategy

Description of risk (Low/Medium/High)	WPs involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Lack of overall coordination Likelihood: low	WP1	Effective coordination is ensured by the managerial structure and through the project work plan. In particular, a Steering Committee, composed by WP leaders, is set up and will be held every 6 months or called by the Coordinator whenever needed. Reporting and communication activities are already foreseen as well as the elaboration of a Data Management Plan and a Quality Assurance Plan. In case of unforeseen events, other experienced persons at the coordinating organisation or at other partners can take over coordination tasks.
Consortium disruption Likelihood: low	WP1	All partners have experience and proven track records in large projects at International, European, national, and local level. All partners are motivated to reach the project objectives, which have been defined in the common interest, considering them a strategic tool for the innovation and competitiveness of the entrepreneurial and education ecosystems.
Conflicts in the Consortium Likelihood: low	WP1	A comprehensive Consortium Agreement has been formulated by all partners. The PM will follow strict administrative guidelines and implement actions against partners failing to comply with procedures agreed upon in the CA. The PM will maintain an easily searchable record of all relevant correspondence among partners. All partners have a track record of solving emergent problems in a collegial spirit.

Delays in deliverables Likelihood: medium	All WPs	A quality and monitoring system will be implemented to spot delays and shortcomings; mitigating actions will be discussed with WP-partners involved to keep the project on time. Partners in WPs will appoint project personnel on time. When they possess spare capacity, failure of one will be mitigated quickly at others. In particular, the delivery date of each deliverable has been formulated to meet the need of the project procedures and to mitigate potential delays beforehand without risking to delay the overall project duration.
A partner leaves the project Likelihood: low	All WPs	Partners' expectations will be continuously verified in order to ensure their commitment to the project. The overall Project Management and coordination foreseen in WP1 points to solve this kind of problem. In case it will happen, the project management board as well as the Steering Committee will analyse 2 main options: 1) the substitution of the partner by another one of similar characteristics 2) the assumption and redistribution of tasks among the high number of partners of the project.
The website/platform is not evolving at the same speed as the project Likelihood: medium	WP4, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP7	ENTREPRENEDU foresees the elaboration of a dedicated Dissemination and Communication Plan to be cross-checked and updated throughout the project development. The experience and expertise of the partner F6S in charge of the communication and dissemination activities will avoid such issues and also the competence and expertise of all the other partners will provide backup options and boosting in the activities of promotion in case of necessity. All partners involved in the project have a strong network and community on social media, each of them counting on at least 3 social media accounts of diverse platforms. All partners will also create and share ad hoc content in line with the project's objectives and depending on the specific need during the overall duration of the project.

<p>Low participants to the Hackathon Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP3, WP7</p>	<p>Specific efforts will be put on promotion during the first months of the project as well as before each Hackathon. The consortium will use all its experience to reach higher educational institutions and start-ups to encourage applications, as well as social media tools, F6S platform, and the network of the organisations supporting the project. Local communities, part of each partner network, will be outreached from the beginning of the project thanks to the organisation of an ad hoc event to promote ENTREPRENEDU. Furthermore, Fondazione E. Amaldi and Corallia have direct expertise in the organisation of Hackathons, being involved in the organisation of the CASSINI Hackathons promoted by the EC at local level as well as of the ActInSpace format, meaning that they already have institutions, target audience, and groups, organisations, entrepreneurs, and students that can be easily reached. EBAN has extensive expertise in the organisation of business and investment events and can count on an international network of target audience. Also, most of the partners have contacts or are directly co-founded by Universities or Research Centres. Last but not least, the Dissemination and Communication Plan will support the continuous monitoring of these activities.</p>
<p>The website/platform to launch the call doesn't work. Likelihood: low</p>	<p>WP4, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP7</p>	<p>The experience and expertise of F6S will strongly support the avoidance of issues related to the disruption of the website/platform to launch the call for action into the project activities. Next to it, all the partners will scout from the very beginning the alternatives to always have a backup option not to lose time in the engagement process.</p>
<p>Difficulty to engage external evaluators for the proposals Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP3, WP5</p>	<p>The task leader of the engagement of external evaluators has already identified potential professionals to be involved in the evaluation process as part of their network. Also, Task Stakeholder and Linked initiatives Engagement will be in place by the beginning of the project to reach and attract experts in the different areas. They will be evaluated by all partners.</p>
<p>Prolonged and costly evaluation process. Likelihood: low</p>	<p>WP3</p>	<p>Close monitoring of the evaluation process will flag early problems and allow correcting procedures. The contracts with evaluators will be flexible to allow to increase the workload of some efficient evaluators and reduce that of others if required.</p>
<p>IPR issues not sorted Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP3, WP4, WP5</p>	<p>IPR related to the project is limited and the exploitation model is based on openness of the project's processes. A first draft of the DMP will be produced at M3 and updated.</p>

8 PROJECT COMMUNICATION

Properly communicating on a project is a critical success factor for managing the expectations of the project consortium and the European Commission. The Project Coordinator is responsible for communication between the Project and the EC. The ENTREPRENEDU project uses several mechanisms for ensuring open and frequent communications amongst its members:

1. electronic mails (e-mail) and mailing lists;
2. conference calls;
3. face-to-face meetings.

8.1 Electronic mails and mailing list

E-mail is the main means of interpersonal communication in ENTREPRENEDU. It can be used for information exchanges, minutes of meetings, executive summaries. It is informal, fairly rapid, and well-suited for non-critical information. E-mail distribution lists are maintained (and regularly updated) by Fondazione E. Amaldi, and available to all the partners. Any change concerning people involved and contact details shall be opportunely communicated to Fondazione E. Amaldi.

The following rules should ensure the suitable use of the e-mail communication between project participants:

- address information ONLY to involved parties in communication: do not systematically copy everyone into communications, or if replying to a specific individual, be cautious not to press the 'reply all' function over 'reply'.
- use an explicit Subject title. E-mail addresses on the official ENTREPRENEDU mailing lists will automatically have an identifier appended in front of the subject line, like [ENTREPRENEDU]. When writing emails, the subject should be a clear indication of the content (for instance, "Meeting minutes 2016-03-17").
- in case the email message has an attachment, please use ZIP files to compress information. However, and as a general rule, it is always preferable to upload the file in Google Drive and inform the relevant people of the location of the file and share the related link to the folder or document. Mailing lists have a limit on the size of messages so attachments should be avoided in favour of document storage on the shared ENTREPRENEDU repository. Very large attachments may not be accepted by the recipient server and even modest size attachments (around a few MB) might rapidly cause e-mail quotas to be

exceeded, particularly where recipients are away from the office for an extended period.

The e-mail exchange is the main instrument used by project partners to share information, proposals, and ideas, as well as to prepare deliverables and any other project output (papers, talks, reports for the EC, etc.).

All mailing lists are managed by Fondazione E. Amaldi. Any request to add or remove a member from any of the project mailing lists should therefore be sent directly to Fondazione E. Amaldi.

8.2 Conference calls

Videoconferences and teleconferences should be scheduled at least a week in advance and should follow a set agenda. To hold conference calls, Google Meet or Zoom are generally used. Telephone is used when personal interaction, a fast answer or reliable confirmation is needed. Telephone calls can sometimes be appropriate for urgent matters so it is important that up to date telephone numbers are made available. It is highly recommended to send an e-mail with the conclusion of a telephone call to limit any ambiguity.

Regularly scheduled conference calls are the primary means of detailed communication between the WPLs, work package members, and deliverable teams. Overall, project plenary calls are held on a monthly basis to ensure that all work package leaders are informed of any upcoming events, issues that may have arisen since the last call or new factors that may have a bearing on the project. In addition to plenary calls, technical calls could be held on a bi-weekly basis to ensure that the work being performed in the different WPs integrate into the overall service architecture. A fixed day of the week and time were decided, in order to simplify organisation of the plenary and technical calls (last Thursday of each month, 3:00 pm - CET - Rome Time). At least one member from each partner organisation is expected to attend the conference calls. During the call, WPLs are responsible for coordinating their work package teams and hold related conference calls. If needed, the WPLs can add more conference calls to the fixed schedule. Formal discussions between WPLs are held on a regular basis to ensure that each WP is being developed in order to support the other WPs. WP leaders propose more conference calls when the implementation of the work requires it, at least a week in advance.

Conference call minutes are produced right after the meeting in a schematic way, which allows all ENTREPRENEDU team to keep track of what was decided during the discussion in a series of action points. All the minutes are available to participants for consultation and are stored in the shared repository.

8.3 Meetings

Currently, ENTREPRENEDU has identified the following categories of meetings:

- Monthly meetings with PC, PM, and WPL. Online meetings, starting in February 2023, fixed date and timing (1h or more according to the consortium’s needs) agreed by the whole consortium, happen every last Thursday of the month at 3:00 pm CET, unless agreed otherwise.
- General Assembly meetings with SC. In person meetings, every 6 months (twice a year), if possible in conjunction with local events and academies organisation.

Below a schedule for the first year of activity:

Agreed Monthly meetings schedule for the first year

Monthly Meeting #1	23/02/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #2	30/03/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #3	27/04/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #4	25/05/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #5	29/06/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #6	27/07/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #7	31/08/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #8	21/09/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #9	26/10/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #10	30/11/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #11	21/12/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #12	25/01/24	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #13	29/02/24	15:00 CET

Provisional General Assemblies schedule

1. M1 | 30.01-01.02.2023: in Rome during the k.o. ✓
2. M5/M6: After the 1st Hackathon in Italy (TBC)
3. M11: in Rome during the NSE Expoforum
4. M18 2024: Concurrently with the interim report
5. M23 December 2024: TBC
6. M29/M30 2025: Rome or Brussels

8.4 ENTREPRENEDU project website

The ENTREPRENEDU project website (<https://entreprenedu.eu/>) is one of the main tools for disseminating information about the consortium and the achievements of the project, providing visitors with comprehensive information about its context and objectives.

The main ENTREPRENEDU website is deployed in English. The home page also hosts the links to ENTREPRENEDU social media accounts. The ENTREPRENEDU website also has a Public Documents area containing the links to public documents that each visitor can download. The website will also be used to involve external stakeholders in the ENTREPRENEDU activities. Publicity material and publications will be made available or referenced. External users will thus find downloadable public documents from the project, notices on conferences either hosted by the ENTREPRENEDU team or where the team will be presenting information on the project, academic papers generated by project team members concerning the project, and other documents that provide valuable insights on what the project is all about to external parties.

The website is developed and updated on a regular basis by F6S. For more information on the ENTREPRENEDU website see project deliverable D7.1 - Dissemination and Communication Plan.

8.5 Document repository

As a primary tool to facilitate exchange of information, a shared web-based collaborative environment has been set up which serves as a project tracking system accessible to all partners, so that all information/documentation is easily accessible and kept up to date with little effort. A Google Drive repository for the ENTREPRENEDU project has been created which gathers all sorts of documents

generated during the project lifetime. Google Drive is a file storage and synchronisation service which allows users to store files on the cloud, share files, and edit documents, spreadsheets, and presentations with collaborators.

Besides being a repository of information it is a common environment for the day-to-day work enabling several users to edit and upload files without overwriting them (working documents, drafts, templates). A set of folders has been created and shared among a definite list of representatives from each partner organisation. Requests for access should be addressed to the PC.

Documents must be uploaded under their corresponding folder and must be named in a clear way so that everybody can have an idea of what the file is about.

Google Drive also supports revision history, so files accidentally deleted could be recovered from any synced computers or directly from the service web interface. The documents contained in Google Drive are in several formats, but all modifiable.

8.6 ENTREPRENEDU project templates

To ensure consistency in the ENTREPRENEDU project, when communicating with external stakeholders or interested parties, a set of standard templates for various communications activities has been developed. These templates include:

1. Deliverable template standard
2. PowerPoint presentation template
3. Standard logos for the project

8.7 ENTREPRENEDU shared calendar

A Google Calendar specifically created for the ENTREPRENEDU project has been shared among all partners. Anyone who wants to use it can easily, securely, and quickly organise meetings, add events, schedule appointments, manage deadlines.

Benefits:

- A. share the project calendar with everyone in the team;
- B. organise team meetings and keep the team informed;
- C. stay up-to-date on appointments through automatic reminders;
- D. keep all your deadlines coordinated from a single place.

9 PROJECT REPORTING

Each Partner generates an internal technical report for each WP, edited by the WPL every year, to be collected by the PM. The PC will be informed in case of any inconsistencies, or unexpected management of resources. Each partner is committed to provide to the PM all the necessary information and documentation to prepare the official periodic reports to be submitted to the European Commission. The reporting includes information about the technical progress, results obtained (e.g., deliverables), the compliance with the work programme and all the relevant information at management level (resources, costs, delays). The PC synthesises the overall project status and planning and compiles the reports due to the EC. The following report is prepared and officially supplied by the PC:

- Periodic report. The periodic report is expected in M18 and must include:
 - an “interim technical report” with a summary of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
 - any other information that will be requested by the PA as relevant.
- Final activity report. The final report is expected in M30 and must include the following:
 - a ‘final technical report’ with a summary for publication containing: an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination; the conclusions on the action, the socio-economic impact of the action;
 - a ‘final financial report’ containing: a ‘final summary financial statement’, created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance.

The PC must submit the final report within 60 days following the end of the reporting period. For reporting at project level, regular review meetings are organised to provide the European Commission and the Consortium with information on the status of the project.

10 CHANGE MANAGEMENT

Change management is the exercise of establishing procedures to assess, approve or disapprove, implement, release, and disseminate changes to agreed specifications and baselines. Change management ensures that configured items are always maintained in a known state or condition. This method of controlling changes guarantees that only approved modifications to existing data are allowed and only these are applied.

The purpose of the ENTREPRENEDU change management is to document how changes are managed throughout the project life cycle. It defines the activities and processes related to managing changes for the ENTREPRENEDU project.

Change requests are made to expand or reduce the project scope, modify operational policies, processes, plans or procedures, revise schedule.

A multi-level approach is used to approve change requests; the authority limits dictate when it is necessary to escalate the change request to a higher level for review and approval:

- the Project Manager makes the final decisions to analyse and proceed with changes if the changes have little or no impact on scope, budget or schedule or result in any increased risk for the project.
- changes which have little or medium impact on scope, budget or schedule are forwarded to the PC for review.
- the SC discusses requests that may result in a significant change in scope, schedule, and budget, and makes the final decision based upon the information provided by the Project Manager and the inputs of the PC.

Each request is tracked from the time of presentation through the following actions:

1. Identify (identify and document the required change)
2. Validate (verify the change is valid and requires management)
3. Analyse (analyse schedule, cost and effort impact of change)
4. Control (decide whether to execute the change)
5. Action (execute decision, including revision to project plans if necessary)
6. Close (verify that action is complete and close change request)

10.1 Document change process

The reason for a change (both corrections and enhancements) of any document must be clearly documented in the change history of the document. The change reason must be stated clearly and the significant changes shall be listed with page numbers so that the new text can easily be recognised and distinguished from the previous text.

After a change is requested, the responsible and/or work package leader analyses its impact on the deliverable itself as well as on the other project outcomes. They may consult with the Project Coordinator.

When the change is evaluated, it may become approved or disapproved. The editor informs the originator of the change request and all contractors involved on the results of evaluation. If the change is disapproved, the editor also presents reasons for their decision within the change request form, which may lead to a further discussion eventually leading to a clear accept or reject decision.

If the change is approved, the editor must implement the changes. After completion, a new draft version of the deliverable is issued for approval or release.

11 CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the approach taken by the ENTREPRENEDU team to manage the quality of the project management. The QAP has to be considered as a guiding document to guarantee that the project will adhere to the original work plan with a proper degree of quality. In addition, the tools used by the team to manage the project, communicate internally and externally about the project and to control the quality and risks associated with the project have been presented. The project quality management plan and the various instruments used to control the project will be continuously updated and refined as the project moves forward. As this is a living document, changes will be made as the project advances and partners develop more components of the project. The next formal update of the present document is set in M30 as part of deliverable 1.6 - "Quality Assurance Plan - final release".